

**UN Task Force on Pandemic Prevention in an Age of
Risky Research, Synthetic Biology, Artificial Intelligence, and the Potential for Bioterrorism
Proposal by Steven Quay, MD, PhD
19 June 2025 – Version 3**

Summary. The Biological Weapons Treaty of 1975 is the only existing international treaty that has the potential to impact dangerous pathogen research, both civilian and military. To set the stage for discussing options for reform, a brief history of the treaty itself is appropriate.

The History of the BWC

The Biological Weapons Convention (BWC), formally enacted in 1975, is the world's foundational treaty banning the development, production, and stockpiling of biological and toxin weapons. But its origins trace back further—to a time when the dangers of biological warfare were still largely theoretical.

In the late 1960s, a working group in Stockholm, in parallel with efforts within the British government, conducted foundational meetings during the formative drafting stages. These efforts culminated in the British presenting the first formal proposals at the Eighteen Nation Disarmament Committee (ENDC) in Geneva. The groundwork laid by the Stockholm group between 1968 and 1969 was eventually published as a six-volume series titled *The Problem of Chemical and Biological Warfare (1969–1973)*, which laid the intellectual and ethical scaffolding for what would become the BWC.

Importantly, the treaty was born without enforcement or verification mechanisms, a weakness that remains today. Since its inception, only one consultative meeting under Article V has ever been convened. That rare occasion occurred in 1987 at the request of Cuba, alleging that the U.S. had released the plant pest, *Thrips palmi*, over its territory. The charge was widely viewed as baseless, but the event demonstrated how Article V might be invoked for political purposes. Notably, the U.S., if accused, would almost certainly never be the state party to call such a meeting. This practical limitation underscores the fragility of enforcement mechanisms in the current BWC framework.

Calls to “amend” the BWC misunderstand both the legal structure and the geopolitical risk. Any effort to open the treaty for amendment would create an opportunity for Russia, China, or Iran to dilute or dismantle its key provisions. Indeed, in 2001, under the incoming Bush administration, the United States terminated negotiations on a verification protocol, arguing, at the time, that it would jeopardize national security and industrial confidentiality. Since 2009, and accelerating sharply in 2018–2019, Russia has taken active steps to undermine the BWC itself, not just its protocols.

For these reasons, those advocating reform must do so with precision. Proposals must be anchored in the treaty's existing instruments, such as calling for a consultative conference under Article V or VI, not through an ill-advised effort to amend the treaty's language. As has been warned, without a precious path forward, doing so would not improve the BWC but instead open the floodgates to its unraveling. But some BWC authors who insist on leaving the BWC untouched do not account for the treaties failure to stop the COVID-19 pandemic or its toothless measures to stop the next pandemic. They seem more interested in keeping their legacy of BWC authorship in the history books than admit it is a failed document.

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Understanding the BWC's fragile legal architecture and its history of both idealism and obstruction is vital. Any effort to build a 21st-century biosafety regime must begin not with rewriting history, but by building technically verifiable safeguards atop its existing legal foundation.

A Twenty-First Century United Nations Proposal

This is a proposal to establish a UN 'Task Force,'¹ with three fact-finding goals and authority to make recommendations to the UN for new or modified treaties and protocols:

Stage One. Fact-finding exercise and objectives

1. Perform an after-action report on the impact of COVID-19;
2. Establish the historical record of laboratory-acquired infections and natural spillovers, excluding and taking no position on the question of the origin of SARS-CoV-2,
3. Provide a report for policy makers, like climate reports, on the potential for risk and benefits of research with dangerous pathogens, the proliferation of high-containment laboratories, and the variety of national efforts to mitigate risky research.²

Stage Two. Recommendations for UN action.

1. Establish a Consultative Conference under Article V or VI of the Biological Weapons Convention (BWC) based on the above findings.
2. Establish UN monitoring protocols for cross border international travel and other critical activities.

The aspirational outcome of the Task Forces work

Resolved. In the interests of preserving the health and security of the world's population, the United Nations intends to:

1. Augment The Biological Weapons Convention to permit the monitoring and unannounced inspection of any and all BSL-3 and BSL-4 laboratories to determine that research on Select Agents and Synthetic Select Agents is conducted for legitimate global health objectives, with a favorable risk-benefit analysis, and that international safety standards are being maintained. A forensic examination protocol would have to be developed to avoid the curated tour of the WIV that the WHO conducted, making the effort a theatrical event.

¹ The UN doesn't form task forces without votes of member states. In this case the state parties to the BWC would have to vote to establish a workgroup. The primary agency at the UN that would have to be engaged would be the Office of Disarmament Affairs. The Biological Weapons Convention last met in late 2022 for its 9th review conference. They meet every 5 years with a Preparatory Conference that meets two years before. The next one would be probably in the Fall of 2025. Typically, an established NGO such as Nuclear Threat Institute or another NGO / Arms Control Association etc. with the staff and financial resources would take on this effort.

² The mechanics are the issue. Who would do the work, where would the work be located/"centered," and organized?

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Having done three separate forensic studies and finding undisclosed influenza, Nipah, and MERS viruses.³

2. Establish an Early Warning System to monitor international travel, specifically:
 - a. Wastewater samples from select airports and specific flights, for pathogens either using PCR or NGS with AI analysis, with the authority to limit outbound traffic for short periods.
 - b. Wastewater samples from live animal markets, using the same techniques as in a. above. One could argue that monitoring the air travel industry might be sufficient and could avoid an appearance of bias against the equatorial wildlife trade.

Stage One: Fact Finding Exercise and Objectives.

- After-action analysis of the COVID-19
 - A report will be generated that provides the infectivity rate, using the R_0 or other accepted parameter, as well as the pathogenicity rate, using healthcare visits, hospitalizations, ICU admissions, and death rates or other accepted parameters, and the level of asymptomatic spread over the course of the pandemic. This is an important property to measure as it was unprecedented for a novel, respiratory virus and could have been engineered into the virus.
 - Because of the potential for recommending future mitigating actions, the role of international air travel on the spread of COVID should be analyzed. The purpose is to see if there is a ‘country-specific’ signal of local disease that could be used as a trigger for universal PCR screening for cross-border travel or even an automatic travel ban and the best duration, whether a few days or up to two weeks
 - This should be mapped over the timeframe, ideally quarterly or semi-annually, from 2000 to May 2023, when the WHO and the US CDC determined the pandemic was over
 - A separate analysis of the May 2023 to latest date, to examine if the decision to declare the pandemic over, turned out to be wise or otherwise
 - The worldwide economic damage caused by the pandemic from a global perspective
 - Also, regional variations in economic outcomes to expose disparate outcomes based on race, income inequality, educational inequality, etc.
- Given the properties of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and the impact it had as measured in the above after-action analysis, model the impact of a hypothetical virus with different infectivity, pathogenicity, and asymptomatic spread

³ This may be a bridge too far at this point. An important part of any multi-lateral endeavor like this is sponsorship. To get any traction would require at major power, US/UK even Sweden or Germany to want to “take ownership” of such an effort. Russia, China, US, UK and a few others wield power with smaller states. It might be advisable to work to get consensus around “lab safety” and push for some voluntary disclosures that might be consistent with Article X under the “exchange of information”. These can take the form of Confidence Building Measures or CBMs. States Parties are loathe to miss them or not participate.

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- Using the supply chains of fossil fuel energy production and distribution, food production and distribution supply chains, the level of fire and police protection, and the staffing and effectiveness of healthcare, from clinics to hospitals, model what properties of a pathogen would be needed to ‘break civilization’
 - The definition of what is a ‘broken civilization’ would need to be agreed on
- Modelling will also try to determine the path, both time, money, and human suffering, to get back to the world ante bellum.
- The purpose of this section is to ‘focus the mind’ of delegates of the responsibility of preventing the next pandemic and the consequences of failing to do so.
- There should be a section on the history of pandemics and their role in changing the world order and history, beginning with the Antonine Plague of 165-180 AD
- A laboratory acquired infection (LAI) report
 - One of the purposes of this work is to come to a UN-agreed sense of the magnitude of LAIs. This will allow China, the US, etc. to come to terms and agreement that the risks of LAIs are real, they have been documents in the past, and there is no reason to believe the rate will go down in the future
 - A minority group can try to model an entirely robotic laboratory if they want but my thinking shows this will have roughly the same LAI, just via different mechanisms
 - Mandatory infrared temperature assessments at all points of entry and exit of laboratories would be a simple but effective tool to put in place.
 - Mandatory wastewater surveillance testing onsite.
- A report on natural spillover zoonoses, extent, locations, outcomes, etc.
 - A UN-based report on the true extent of this problem would be important. The western world seems quite willing to call out Asian cultures of live animal markets that have a millennium of tradition and demand their closure. Only the UN can negotiate these views.⁴
 - The report can include the role of the expanding human-nature interface as people expand into natural areas and the impact of a new interface has on the potential for a pandemic. Climate change can be included here although much of the scientific work on the true role of climate does not withstand the scrutiny of detailed examination and seems more written to secure favorable funding for more work or to meet a backward, results driven agenda to create false findings to drive a political agenda.
- A report on the proliferation of BSL-3 and BSL-4 laboratories and the expansion into regions with unstable governments
- The status of Synthetic Biology of infectious agents⁵

⁴This could also be WHO or BWC.

⁵ Back to the UN here, IF and its a big IF (money/people/logistics) you could organize such an effort to begin to produce papers there are mechanisms for NGOs to present papers for consideration. For example, in the run up to the 2027 review conference, late next year the states parties will meet in Geneva for the “predatory conference”. This

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- Ask a group of US, Chinese, and EU scientists to write a report on the potential impact of the tools of synthetic biology on viral research. That is, describe the limits of serial passage for host tropism, is it different with different classes of pathogens, etc. Describe the potential and limits of reverse genetic systems and infections clones in bacteria, yeast, etc. The role and use of transgenic animal models in infectious disease research.
- Artificial intelligence and pathogen research
 - This is the weakest element in this proposal and could be eliminated. If included the purpose would be to predict how AI could accelerate the synthetic biology of pathogens.
- Biosafety and Biosecurity Post COVID
 - A report on the status of existing protocols and procedures for biosafety and biosecurity pre-pandemic and the changes and learnings for the largest pandemic in a century. What did you wish was in place before the pandemic with respect to biosecurity and biosafety?
- Prospects of bioterrorism from synthetic biology
 - The BWC should establish a working group at the 2027 review conference to provide a report on bioterrorism and synthetic biology. This could be a confidential report because of its sensitivity.
- National steps being proposed to address these issues
 - A report on the history of the GoF Research Pause in the US, how it came about, what were the legal details, and the structure of the PC3O system that came out of it. This has been deemed in retrospect to have been a failure and the reasons for that conclusion need to be set out.
 - The US Senate's bill titled the Risky Research Review Act⁶ could be introduced as one approach to address this issue.
 - The White House also had a proposal and that should be included here as well.
 - Other countries would be invited to add their own versions of bills, laws, etc. from which common themes, pros and cons, etc. could be drawn.
 - A summary table of all of the efforts would be part of this section.

Stage 2: Recommendations of the UN based on the fact finding.

This is speculative because I am writing without the basis of the report, but you can see the two changes I am proposing above in the introduction.

Definition of a new term.

is a time when NGOs meet, sponsor events, talks, seminars to generate attention to whatever issue they might be trying to push forward. This takes time and \$\$ and people. But it can be done and is done. Well-funded leftist NGOs funded by Gates, Carnegie, Soros, MacArthur and others support the arms control left to the tune of about \$100 mil per year. And this is how they advocate and push through their agenda.

⁶ <https://www.hsgac.senate.gov/wp-content/uploads/Risky-Research-Review-Act.pdf>

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Synthetic Select Agent – A currently defined Select Agent in which the genetic sequence has been modified in a laboratory from one nucleotide to up to 35% of the non-modified genetic sequence. This threshold is set to allow 100% synonymous mutations. In reality, this is a high level of substitution that would probably lead to a non-viable organism and provides a conservative way of setting a boundary.